

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators

Actionable
version

Definition

The Indicators guide 1 supports responsible research assessment (RRA) with a special focus on open science (OS) contributions. It provides guidance on how to select, interpret, and apply indicators and metrics in a way that balances quantitative measures with qualitative judgment. Its main purpose is to help institutions use indicators transparently, responsibly, and in alignment with their values.

Relevant SCOPE stages

- Options for evaluating: Choosing appropriate indicators and metrics.
- Probe deeply: Interpreting data critically and acknowledging limitations.

When and how to use

Use the guide when:

- Designing or revising research assessment processes (e.g., for hiring, promotion, funding).
- Developing balanced evaluation frameworks that combine quantitative metrics with qualitative expert assessment.
- Benchmarking at institutional, national, or disciplinary levels.
- Introducing or strengthening recognition of open science practices in career assessment.

How to use:

- Define purpose and values → What do you want to measure, and why?
- Select indicators responsibly → Use multiple indicators instead of relying on a single metric.
- Balance methods → Combine metrics (e.g., citations, downloads, collaboration data) with qualitative evaluation (peer review, narrative CVs).
- Ensure transparency → Clearly state which indicators are used, their data sources, and limitations.
- Revisit regularly → Assess whether chosen indicators remain fit for purpose.

Guidance

- Avoid misuse of metrics: Journal Impact Factor and H-index should not be applied in evaluating individual researchers.
- Context matters: Citation and publication practices differ across disciplines. Always interpret metrics relative to the field, values and purpose of the evaluation.
- Prioritise openness: Use open and non-commercial infrastructures (OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, BIP!Services, OpenCitations).

- Highlight OS practices: Consider indicators for open access, FAIR data, open peer review, collaboration, and societal impact.
- Remember limitations: Indicators often reflect past activity and miss broader contributions like teaching or mentoring.
- Interpret cautiously, especially for individuals.

Further reading

SCOPE+i Resources

- Indicators Guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862>
- Open Science assessment guide. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>
- Guide on choosing an assessment method <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>

Other

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- Leiden Manifesto: <https://www.leidenmanifesto.org/>
- DORA Declaration & Guidance: <https://sfedora.org/read/>

